

IMPORTANCE OF COLORS AND THEIR IMPLEMENTATION

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COLOR PERSONALITY

Science has long recognised that colour affects our behaviour and the way we feel. After all, it is the first thing we register and that we use to help assess the things around us, such as whether certain foods, such as blue ones, might be poisonous, for example.

To understand these responses, we need to look at how colour works. Essentially, when the light reflected from coloured objects strikes the retinas in our eyes, the wavelengths are converted into electrical impulses. These pass into the part of the brain that rules our hormones and endocrine system, which are instrumental in regulating our moods. Unconsciously, then, our eyes and bodies constantly adapt to these stimuli, influencing our impulses and perceptions.

COLOR PSYCHOLOGY AS THERAPY

Several ancient cultures, including the Egyptians and Chinese, practiced chromotherapy, or the use of colors to heal. Chromotherapy is sometimes referred to as light therapy or colourology and is still used today as a holistic or alternative treatment.

In this treatment:

- **Red** was used to stimulate the body and mind and to increase circulation.
- **Yellow** was thought to stimulate the nerves and purify the body.
- **Orange** was used to heal the lungs and to increase energy levels.
- **Blue** was believed to soothe illnesses and treat pain.
- **Indigo** shades were thought to alleviate skin problems.

COLOR AND CULTURE

Much of a color's effect may be due to meanings assigned to that color within a given culture, which can vary widely from one culture to another.

For example,

- While the color white is used in many Western countries to represent purity and innocence, it is seen as a symbol of mourning in many Eastern countries. In the US, for example, brides wear white, but in some asian cultures white is associated with death and mourning.
- Even within the same culture, colors can have different (sometimes even opposing) meanings based on context. The bad guy may wear black, but so do judges in the courtroom. Red can be a warning of impending danger, but cards bearing red hearts are exchanged on Valentine's Day.
- Individuals also have their own subjective color preferences, and often have unique associations to specific colors, as well. If your grandfather always drove a bright yellow

jeep (as mine did), for example, then you may subconsciously associate bright yellow with feelings of happiness.

COLOR MEANINGS ---Clearly, using color to affect mood and behavior is not an exact science. The variables are too many, and the differences in response from one individual to the next are too great. Still, research suggests that some colors may tend to have measurable physiological effects on many people, if not all.

Culturally-learned meanings of color are also quite powerful, and can be used to subtly affect mood and behaviour in some people. The following list discusses some of the meanings commonly associated with various colors in the US and other western societies, as well as the results of scientific study on specific colors where applicable:

Red: represents danger, warning, or error, but also warmth, love, passion, and intense emotion. Can also symbolize bravery, war, or blood. Some studies have shown it to stimulate appetite (which is why there's so much red at McDonald's restaurants) and improve accuracy on certain tasks.

Pink: the lighter shade of red represents love and romance, as well as femininity. Pink is generally considered to have a calming effect.

Yellow: this bright, attention-getting color is seen as a sunny, happy color, yet studies have also shown, paradoxically, that prolonged exposure to it can make adults lose their tempers and babies cry. Yellow is also the most fatiguing color to the eye.

Blue: seen as having a calming effect. Darker shades of blue (as in police uniforms and business suits) may suggest reliability and security. The color is also often associated with sadness. Studies suggest that the color blue can increase productivity and creativity, and may actually lower body temperature and pulse rate.

Orange: being a combination of yellow and red, orange is also a warm, stimulating and attention-getting color.

Brown: darker shades of red, yellow and orange are warm, but less stimulating. These earthy colors can suggest strength and security.

Green: a combination of blue and yellow, this color is generally a physically soothing color that may simultaneously produce an emotional lift. Green is the color most associated with nature, and sometimes signifies good luck or money (which may be why at its extreme, green is associated with envy).

Purple: associated with royalty, wealth, and luxury, as well as spirituality and wisdom. Purple can seem exotic, but sometimes overly so. In some instances purple can appear out of place or even artificial.

White: represents purity, innocence, and goodness (the good guy is the one in the white hat). White makes a room seem brighter and more spacious, but too much white can have a sterile, cold effect.

Black: represents death, mourning, and evil (think Darth Vader), but also sophistication, as in formal wear, and authority, as in a judge's robe.

Gray: literally a "middle-of-the-road" color, gray is a practical, timeless color, but also dull or even depressing when used in excess. Gray causes the least eye fatigue of any color.

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